

Working Paper

From Cooperative To Coercive Federalism?
The Legislative Function Under Next
Generation EU And The Federal Genus Of
Union Law

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FROM COOPERATIVE TO COERCIVE FEDERALISM? THE LEGISLATIVE FUNCTION UNDER NEXT GENERATION EU AND THE FEDERAL GENUS OF UNION LAW

Alastair MacIver*

Abstract

This Working Paper examines what Next Generation EU (NGEU) does to the structure of federalism in the EU. It draws a comparison between the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and conditional spending programmes in US, Australian and Canadian federalism to identify a heuristic framework for determining when funding to (Member) States crosses the line between policy leverage and a form of federal coercion. While, after the RRF, the cohesion legal basis takes on features in common with the US “general welfare clause”, the Working Paper argues that the RRF does not have an unambiguously coercive character that satisfies the definition of compulsion gleaned from comparative federal jurisprudence. With that template, the Working Paper puts forward tools to understand if the RRF and its putative “de-crisisified” successor leave sufficient policy space for Member States and their legislatures to exercise real choice regarding the acceptance of funds, based on the size, granularity and extraneousness of conditional spending.

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1. Introduction: Law-making, spending, spending for law-making

Next Generation EU (NGEU) constitutes a major achievement of the European project and of native legal cunning. As the principal vehicle to mobilise financing, through Recovery and Resilience Plans (RRPs), it responds to the deep and unprecedented economic and social impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, and now¹ the succeeding energy crisis precipitated by the Ukraine war. The complex *machine à gaz* to which NGEU gives birth equips the Economic and Monetary Union (EMU), and the Union as a whole, with a fiscal capacity and might well presage a pivot from “negative” to “positive”² instruments of economic policy coordination. Time will tell whether the former subsumes the latter through the “enforcement of reforms and investments” in the “national medium-term fiscal-structural plans” proposed as successors to the RRP.s.³ For now, NGEU heralds the start of the transformation from a “rules-based” to a “fiscal-capacity-based” architecture of Schlosser’s “New Fiscal Union”⁴. Analyses of NGEU have been wide-ranging in their focus. Alleged “accounting slights-of-hand”⁵ in back-to-back borrowing enabled by the Own Resources Decision (ORD)⁶ and European Union Recovery Instrument (EURI)⁷ notwithstanding, this paper focuses on the *spending side* of the balance sheet and what it argues to be the fundamental transformation in the *legislative function* brought about by NGEU in its Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF). Drawing on Schütze’s federal understanding of the Union⁸ and the place of the legislative function (how legislative power is divided between the Union and the Member States) in that framework, it will raise the possibility of a change in the structure of Union from cooperative to coercive (or regulatory) federalism, at least as regards NGEU, if not across the board. The claim

¹ Council of the European Union, Press Release, “EU recovery plan: Provisional agreement reached on REPowerEU”, 14 December 2022. Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/12/14/eu-recovery-plan-provisional-agreement-reached-on-repowerEU/> See the original adopted RRF Regulation: Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 February 2021 establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility, OJ L 57, 18.2.2021, p. 17–75.

² P. Dermine, “The EU’s Response to the COVID-19 Crisis and the Trajectory of Fiscal Integration in Europe: Between Continuity and Rupture” (2020) 47(4) *Legal Issues of Economic Integration* 337..

³ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Central Bank, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Communication on Orientations for a Reform of the EU Economic Governance Framework, Brussels, 9.11.2022, COM(2022) 583 final, p.18.

⁴ P. Schlosser, *Europe’s New Fiscal Union* (Springer International Publishing, 2018).

⁵ P. Dermine (n 2)

⁶ Council Decision (EU, Euratom) 2020/2053 of 14 December 2020 on the system of own resources of the European Union and repealing Decision 2014/335/EU, Euratom OJ L 424, 15.12.2020, p. 1–10.

⁷ Council Regulation (EU) 2020/2094 of 14 December 2020 establishing a European Union Recovery Instrument to support the recovery in the aftermath of the COVID-19 crisis OJ L 433I, 22.12.2020, p. 23–27.

⁸ R. Schütze, *From Dual to Cooperative Federalism: The Changing Structure of European Law* (Oxford: OUP, 2009).

that the Union is host to cooperative federalism is Schütze's well-known view⁹; on the other hand, Kincaid identifies coercive federalism in other jurisdictions as a collateral effect of "the habit of federal activism and the nationalist momentum built up under cooperative federalism" and the collapse of liberal conditions for federal action in pursuit of social equity.¹⁰ This paper examines whether the range, intensity and conditions for funding under RRF harbour the potential for coercive federalism by using Union funding as a lever to incentivise national policy and regulatory law-making where the Union *cannot otherwise make law*.

As such, coercive federalism has a number of hallmarks, but the feature examined briefly by this paper is of that of regulatory conditionality attached to federal (or Union) grants to the (Member) States. Of course, in the EU, spending entailed by such grants does not stand outside the vertical division of competences: unlike the enumeration principle found in other federations, the principle of conferral in Article 5(2) TEU referred to Union to "*act only within the limits of the competences conferred*". *Action*, in this sense, covers both *law-making and spending*, as Article 310(3) TFEU further confirms through the ideas of a *double legal basis* and *prior adoption*. In that sense, all EU spending is conditional spending. However, in the context of the framework of coercive federalism, the paper turns to a sub-set of Union action in conferred fields of action: *spending for (Member State) law-making*. The RRF provides for such spending for law-making and has a sound cohesion legal basis to do so: Article 175(3) TFEU. This paper does not argue that the RRF Regulation is *ultra vires*, but the capaciousness of the cohesion legal basis does allow for the promotion of law-making that could not otherwise be effected by the legal bases in other Union regulatory policy frameworks. In the language of American federalism, one can describe the promotion of many such reforms outside otherwise conferred legislative competences as *extraneous ends of the general welfare*.¹¹ Armstrong¹² has pointed out the same phenomenon of extraneous ends by using Daintith's distinction: whereas law-making is an example of *imperium*, the "power of money to achieve socially desirable ends" is an example of *dominium*.¹³ The conceptually distinct notion of *dominium* elides, or at least re-contextualises, the conferral principle and the pursuit of objectives by spending in virtually any policy field.

⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰ J. Kincaid, "From Cooperative to Coercive Federalism" (1990) *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 509(1), 139–152.

¹¹ D. E. Engdahl, "The Spending Power" (1994) 44(1) *Duke Law Journal* 5-26.

¹² K. Armstrong, "EU social policy and the governance architecture of Europe 2020", *Queen Mary University of London, School of Law Legal Studies Research Paper No. 110/2012*.

¹³ T. Daintith "Legal Analysis of Economic Policy" (1982) 9 (2) *Journal of Law and Society* 191-224.

Without using federal vocabulary, the RRF architecture plays host only to a form of conditionality that promotes reforms and investments,¹⁴ albeit in an attenuated way in particular contrast with the European Stability Mechanism, and, in part, due to the non-applicability of the *Pringle*¹⁵ and *Gauweiler*¹⁶ jurisprudence on strict conditionality. The RRF is, at base, a cohesion programme and *ex ante* conditionality is not new to cohesion programmes. Likewise, the confluence of economic policy coordination and cohesion policy is not new,¹⁷ nor is positing Article 175(3) TFEU as a financial clause that may “knowingly”¹⁸ effect economic policy coordination for EMU. However, in addition to its sheer size, a novelty of the RRF, comes from the revision of the Financial Regulation in 2018 introduced the new instrument, the “*financing not linked to costs*” (“FNLTC”) model.¹⁹ FNLTC is a fundamentally new method of EU funding, deployed in the RRF, based on the fulfilment of *milestones* and *targets* set out in the RRFs.²⁰ In that context, this paper argues that the RRF’s extraneous range, granularity inherent in FNLTC and the amount of Union financial support as a percentage of GDP²¹, under a single *omnibus* programme harbour the potential to compel Member States and their legislatures to make law.

In a sense, this problematic re-expresses the perennial issues of competence creep and deparliamentarisation that a host of scholars have pointed out since the euro crisis. However, the federal comparison allows us to build a framework of understanding for the vertical division of power between the Union and Member States and in the horizontal division of competence. It identifies potential analytical tools to understand and mediate emergent problems. While the use of Article 175(3) TFEU holds legal water and vindicates the ingenuity of institutional lawyers,

¹⁴ B. De Witte, “The European Union’s COVID-19 recovery plan: The legal engineering of an economic policy shift” (2021) 58(3) *Common Market Law Review* 635. ; P. Delmine,(n 2).

¹⁵ Case C-370/12, *Pringle*, ECLI:EU:C:2012:756.

¹⁶ Case C-62/14, *Gauweiler*, ECLI:EU:C:2015:400.

¹⁷ C. Scheinert and C. van Lierop, “Linking cohesion policy and the European Semester Partnership and multi-level governance to boost investment and structural reforms”, Study, *European Parliament Research Service*, PE 644.208, December 2019. Available at:

[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/644208/EPRS_STU\(2019\)644208_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/644208/EPRS_STU(2019)644208_EN.pdf); A. Hunter, “From mission letter to mission impossible: can a top-down approach to ‘Cohesion and Reforms’ really deliver?”, Commentary, *European Policy Centre*, 24 September 2019. Available at: <https://epc.eu/en/Publications/From-mission-letter-to-mission-impossible-Can-a-top-down-approach-to-2990a0>

¹⁸ L. Flynn, “Greater Convergence, More Resilience? Cohesion Policy and the Deepening of the Economic and Monetary Union”, in D. Fromage and B. de Witte (eds.), *Recent Evolutions in the Economic and Monetary Union and the European Banking Union: A Reflection*, Faculty of Law Working Paper Series, 2019/03, *Maastricht University*, 2019, p. 49.

¹⁹ Article 125(1), Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2018/1046 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 July 2018 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union, amending Regulations (EU) No 1296/2013, (EU) No 1301/2013, (EU) No 1303/2013, (EU) No 1304/2013, (EU) No 1309/2013, (EU) No 1316/2013, (EU) No 223/2014, (EU) No 283/2014, and Decision No 541/2014/EU and repealing Regulation (EU, Euratom) No 966/2012, OJ L 193, 30.7.2018, p. 1–222

²⁰ Recital 18, RRF Regulation.

²¹ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/infographics/RRF/?lang=en#data-map>

constitutionally speaking, its downstream effect risks eroding the political substance of federalism, as pointed out concerning programmes promoting extraneous ends of the general welfare. Since, as Beaud argues, the federation is fundamentally not a legal, but a “politico-legal”²² concept, it is possible for the RRF’s features to be genuinely characterised “legally feasible, constitutionally dubious”.²³ While RRF ultimately cannot be considered coercive in terms of legal doctrines developed in other federations, far from being a “federalising”²⁴ moment, NGEU could portend the start of a *defederalising* turning point for the EU.

For reasons of space, it is not possible to re-present Schütze’s federal thesis in full here. Nonetheless, in order to make the comparison between federal states and the EU viable and meaningful, it is necessary to clarify the some methodological presuppositions regarding what it meant by federation, adopted from Schütze. In essence, his contention is that European lawyers’ way of thinking about the federation and (in particular its equation with a State) is the inheritance of 19th century state theory.²⁵ One might call it a sovereignty-based theory, whereas he promotes a pact-based theory that, he argues, can be excavated from the *Federalist Papers* and better explains the EU. When we approach the federal language surrounding the NGEU, it has been successful in perpetuating the tendency to regard the “Hamiltonian moment” as the constitutional lens through which to assess a fiscal capacity for the economic and monetary union. Leino-Sandberg and Ruffert define a “Hamiltonian moment” as “the assumption by the US federal government of the remaining part of the States’ War debt”.²⁶ While, in the United States, the Funding Act of 1790 brought about this *debt assumption*, scholars and commentators seem to deny that the EU has yet attained this threshold with NGEU,²⁷ the comparator is a clear facet of the debate. In terms of presuppositions, this kind of analysis ties federal Statehood, and the question of the ultimate locus of sovereignty, more or less implicitly to this Hamiltonian threshold. For instance, in expounding a narrower reading of Article 310(1) TFEU, Leino-Sandberg and Ruffert, juxtapose the EU with a State:

²² O. Beaud, *Théorie de la Fédération* (Paris : Presses Universitaires de France, 2005), p.33. He defines the theory of the federation as the autonomy of the notion of federation conceived as a politico-legal entity. To this end, Beaud attempts to show the both the political and legal elements of the notion: “on a essayé de relier ensemble l’idée politique du fédéralisme et la structuration juridique de la Fédération”.

²³ M. Nettesheim, “Legally Feasible, Constitutionally Dubious: Establishing ‘Next Generation Europe’ on the Basis of EU Secondary Legislation”, *VerfBlog*, 2020/12/04, <https://verfassungsblog.de/legally-feasible-constitutionally-dubious/>, DOI: 10.17176/20201204-175711-0.

²⁴ F. Fabbrini, “Next Generation EU: Legal Structure and Constitutional Consequences”, *REBUILD Centre Working Paper* No. 3 (2022).

²⁵ R. Schütze (n 8), pp. 30-35.

²⁶ P. Leino-Sandberg and M. Ruffert, “Next Generation EU and Its Constitutional Ramifications: A Critical Assessment” (2022) *Common Market Law Review*

²⁷ P. Dermine (n 2).

“Borrowing is for a Treaty-based supranational creature such as the EU is different from borrowing by a State where the required balance between revenue and payment may be implicitly filled by incurring a debt.”

This sort of sovereignty-based conception of federalism, in the light of what Schütze lays out, risks reifying what really gives a polity its federal genus. In this way, to talk deductively of a federation being marked by debt assumption is no different than deductively stipulating the need for it to be constituted by a *demos*.²⁸ By moving beyond sovereignty and going back to Federalist No. 39 (via Kelsen and Schmitt²⁹, who respectively collapse the constitution/treaty dichotomy into the *Grundnorm* and leave the question sovereignty permanently *suspended*), Schütze and others classify the EU as a *federation of States* (no oxymoron) in which the question of sovereignty is avoided (as either shared or twofold) and rechannelled into concrete jurisdictional tests. This move helps us to understand that the EU, even (and, in fact, especially) *qua* “Treaty-based supranational creature”, can be said to be an *actually-existing federation*, and set aside the speculation about whether it is a federal State in incubation, which lies very much in the background of talk of “Hamiltonian” moments. This problematic is raised here, by way of introducing this paper, because, when we turn to NGEU, focussed, for instance, only on the question of “Hamiltonian moment”, it hampers our ability to find the adequate vocabulary, used in other federations, to describe the constitutional change the recovery plan effects to the the legislative function. In particular, we can delineate the legislative function in cooperative federalism: shared national and Union legislative action in pursuit of tasks within conferred sectoral policy fields, based on functional pre-emption. Its portents are the decline of state “police powers” through the expansion of Articles 114 and 352 TFEU and delegation of exclusive competences.³⁰ By contrast, in this paper, we can use the benchmark of coercive federalism to examine the RRF with the features consisting in non-pre-emptive Union legislation that merely sets a framework to offer financial incentives for, but not oblige, the enactment of legislation at national level in a range sectoral policy fields, both inside and outside of Union legislative competence.

The paper will be structured as follows: firstly, the paper will set out conditional spending powers vested in other (allegedly coercive) federations such as Australia, Canada, and the United States, where they were most notably exercised in the *No Child Left Behind (NCLB)*, *Patient Protection*

²⁸ R. Schütze (n 8), pp. 66-68.

²⁹ *Ibid*, pp. 37-39.

³⁰ *Ibid*, pp. 132-184.

ann Affordable Care Act (PPACA) and *National Minimum Drinking Age Acts*. The paper next turns to examination of the RRF. In incentivising policy making at the Member State level, which is structurally designed and approved by the Union often without national parliamentary involvement, NGEU is found to present similar issues to those identified in with regard to States' loss of Medicaid funding *Sebelius*³¹, and in *South Dakota v. Dole*³² with regard to the conditioning of federal funding for highways upon the introduction of a minimum drinking age of 21, by legislation of the several states. While excavating the problematic features of conditional spending programmes for federalism, the judicial tests set out in *Dole*, *Sebelius* and other analogous cases seem, on the whole, to be satisfied, such that coercion is avoided. Nonetheless, given the breadth of the cohesion legal basis, NGEU is shown to harbour the potential to regulate and coerce as regards extraneous ends of the general welfare, especially if tied to densely defined conditions under the European Semester. The paper concludes by considering the implications of exhaustion of the vocabulary of cooperative federalism for democratic accountability for the RRFs.

2. Coercive Federalism and Fiscal Capacities

The establishment of the recovery fund may be fruitfully compared with the general welfare clause, more commonly described as the "Spending Power"³³, in Article I, Section 8, Clause 1 of the United States Constitution:

"The Congress shall have Power To lay and collect Taxes, Duties, Imposts and Excises, to pay the Debts and provide for the common Defence and general Welfare of the United States; but all Duties, Imposts and Excises shall be uniform throughout the United States."

As Engdahl warns, we should not be induced to draw the mistaken conclusion that promotion of the general welfare, rather than merely the act of spending itself, is within Congress' constitutional power.³⁴ As the US Supreme court made clear early on, "the phrase 'to provide for the general welfare' qualifies the power 'to lay and collect taxes.' The view that the clause grants power to provide or the general welfare, independently of the taxing power, has never been authoritatively accepted".³⁵ It was as most notably exercised in the *NCLB*, *PPACA* and *National Minimum Drinking Age Acts*. This section will briefly examine the structure of the *PPACA* and *National*

³¹ *National Federation of Independent Business v. Sebelius* 567 US (2012).

³² *South Dakota v. Dole* 483 US 203 (1987).

³³ cf. D. S. Schwartz, "Recovering the Lost General Welfare Clause", 63 (2022) *Wm. & Mary L. Rev.* 857.

³⁴ D. E. Engdahl, "The Basis of the Spending Power" (1995) 18 *SEATTLE U. L. REV.* 215, 217.

³⁵ *United States v. Butler*, 297 U.S. 1, 64 (1936).

Minimum Drinking Age Act programmes and turn to Australian and Canadian examples and their distinct doctrines limiting the scope of the spending power in order to curtail federal coercion. In incentivising policy-making State level, which is structurally designed and approved by federal government thus presents similar issues of federal regulatory power to those considered by the United States Supreme Court in *South Dakota v. Dole* with regard to the conditioning of federal funding for highways upon the introduction of a minimum drinking age of 21, by legislation of the several states. It was a salient feature of that the Twenty-First of the United States Constitution made legislation on the sale, export and consumption of alcohol the subject of State law-making. The *Dole* tests, we will look at below, were applied to that programme, while the Court found that enumeration principle was not a constitutional bar on the Act and that it was not itself coercive either.³⁶

By contrast, in Canada, the spending power in the Constitution Act of 1982 is implicit³⁷ and spending within fields of exclusionary provincial jurisdiction has a nation-building character that has run against Québec's own national project.³⁸ With awareness of the difficulties of a spending power by implication only, the Section 282 of India's Constitution was drafted to make explicit that the spending powers of the central and state authorities need not track legislative competence: "[t]he Union or a State may make any grants for any public purpose, notwithstanding that the purpose is not one with respect to which Parliament or the Legislature of the State, as the case may be, may make laws." In Australia, the spending power was thought for a long period to be vested in the executive, in Section 61 of the Commonwealth of Australia Constitution Act, until the *Williams (School Chaplains)* cases stipulated the need for prior legislation of Parliament, not unlike Article 310(3) TFEU.³⁹ A provision of a similar kind, enabling Parliament to provide financial assistance, subsists in Section 96.

If we turn immediately to the sorts of objections that are raised as regards conditional spending programmes in federations we will find two groups. The first group are largely dual federalist in

³⁶ "Section 1. The eighteenth article of amendment to the Constitution of the United States is hereby repealed.
Section 2. The transportation or importation into any State, Territory, or possession of the United States for delivery or use therein of intoxicating liquors, in violation of the laws thereof, is hereby prohibited.
Section 3. This article shall be inoperative unless it shall have been ratified as an amendment to the Constitution by conventions in the several States, as provided in the Constitution, within seven years from the date of the submission hereof to the States by the Congress."

³⁷ *Finlay v. Canada (Minister of Finance)* [1986] 2 SCR 607.

³⁸ H.Telford, "The Federal Spending Power in Canada: Nation-Building or Nation-Destroying?" (2003) 33(1) *Publius* 23.

³⁹ *Williams v. Commonwealth* (2012) 248 CLR 156; *Williams v. Commonwealth* (2014) 252 CLR 416.

character and have been levelled against the federal systems of the United States⁴⁰, Canada⁴¹ and Australia.⁴² These objections are predicated on an essentially dual federalist assumption⁴³ because central to this first critique of conditional spending is the conferral or enumeration principle that characterises federations. The allegation is that this principle comes under strain where the central authorities induce law-making at (Member) State level, in a field where they themselves cannot make law, for instance as in the case of that put forward by McCoy and Friedman as regards the US.⁴⁴ In this way, this most rudimentary objection to conditional spending from scholars and political actors in the United States and Canada takes the same line as James Madison: the promotion of law-making by the States in fields should track the enumerated powers of the federal legislature. For our purposes, these objections shed little light on NGEU and we can set this first group to one side, not least because, as noted above, Article 310(3) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) stipulates *prior* Union law-making to enable conditional spending and the cohesion competence provides a conferred power for such law-making and spending in the case of NGEU.

Nonetheless, the Madisonian objection does not exhaust the literature surrounding spending powers and fending it off does not answer all the federal questions presented by the enticements of NGEU. A second approach to spending powers is spelt out principally by the U.S. Supreme Court.

Since the US Supreme Court's judgment in *South Dakota v. Dole*, such Madisonian and dual federalist objections have indeed given way to Alexander Hamilton's view that the spending power should be untethered from the enumeration principle and permitted pursue to *extraneous ends of the general welfare*. The U.S. Supreme Court has thereby established a framework for assessing whether a state is being "forced" to act in a particular way by the federal government, in cases involving federal funding conditions and other forms of federal coercion. The Court looks at whether the funding conditions or penalties imposed by the federal government are "so coercive as to pass the point at which pressure turns into compulsion". Thus, while yielding to conditional spending beyond enumeration, *Dole* however stipulates that conditions for federal funds be:

- 1. unambiguous;

⁴⁰ R. McCoy & B. Friedman, "Conditional Spending: Federalism's Trojan Horse", (1988) *SUP.CT. REV.* 85.

⁴¹ H. Telford (n 42).

⁴² B. Gogarty, "Making Sense of S 96: Tied Grants, Contextualism And The Limits Of Federal Fiscal Power" (2019) 42(2) *Melbourne University Law Review* 455.

⁴³ D. Engdahl (n 11).

⁴⁴ R. McCoy & B. Friedman (n 44).

- 2. respect other constitutional provisions;
- 3.germane;
- 4. and non-coercive.

The latter limitation being applied most notably in the *Sebelius* regarding the provisions of the *PPACA* held to *coerce* states to expand Medicaid by threatening States in the case of non-compliance with the loss of existing Medicaid funding, amounting to more than 10% of the State's total budget. The size of the federal funding to be withheld, then, was indicative of coercion on the fourth limb of *Dole*. This section has shown very briefly that the *Dole* and *Sebelius* limitations, which we find echoed in less articulated form in Canadian and Australian federalism, seek to secure free, informed choice as well as policy space at state level. Those parameters provide a template that embodies the federal conception of the division of powers and supplies framework of assessing the impact of NGEU.

3. Europe's "General Welfare Clause": Is every cohesion thought an afterthought?

The preceding brief survey of coercive federal conditional spending equips us to turn back to the RRF. As we saw, the central aspect of the conditional spending powers we looked at is their essentially *extrajurisdictional* nature in the pursuit of *extraneous ends*. That is, such programmes *spend where the federal legislature cannot make law*. As Leino-Sandberg and Saarenheimo write, looking at the Reform Support Programme and Budgetary Instrument for Convergence and Competitiveness, these extraneous ends are very much in the foreground, whereas cohesion appears to be somewhat of an "afterthought".⁴⁵ Spending of this kind is premised on a fundamentally Hamiltonian view and also ultimately cooperative federalist view, as opposed to dual federalist objections we saw in the first group above that rest on the Madisonian contention that spending should track law-making power. In the European Union, there is nothing at all controversial about conferred powers pursuing extraneous ends, as Engdahl puts it. For a start, this is simply what Schütze describes as part of the "decline of constitutional exclusivity" as a part of cooperative federalism, as held notably in *Tobacco Advertising I*⁴⁶ judgment with respect to Article 114 TFEU. In what follows, however, this section will argue that Article 175(3) TFEU can be characterised as Europe's "General Welfare Clause", to match Europe's Commerce (Article 114 TFEU) and Necessary and Proper Clauses (Article 352 TFEU).⁴⁷ This bears out the analogy that the paper seeks to make and also points to limits on what NGEU might achieve without upsetting the vertical division of power.

In order to start to substantiate this, Article 175(3) TFEU is variously described as "purposive"⁴⁸, "not limited to specific sectors and is defined functionally"⁴⁹, whose contours are unclear insofar as it aims to promote the Union's "overall harmonious development", as indicatively defined in Article 174 TFEU, by "specific actions" that "prove necessary outside the Funds". Notably, in the *International Fund for Ireland* case,⁵⁰ Advocate General Bot portrays Article 174 TFEU, which delineates the scope of Article 175(3) TFEU, as "*permit(ing) a degree of flexibility as well as*

⁴⁵ P. Leino-Sandberg & T. Saarenheimo, "Fiscal Stabilisation for EMU – Managing Incompleteness" (2018) 43 *European Law Review* 639.

⁴⁶ Case C-376/98, *Germany v. Parliament and Council*, ECLI:EU:C:2000:544, paragraph 88; R. Schütze (n 8), pp. 144-145.

⁴⁷ R. Schütze (n 8), pp. 133, 143.

⁴⁸ B. De Witte (n 14).

⁴⁹ Opinion of the Council Legal Service, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on a mechanism to resolve legal and administrative obstacles in a cross-border context, 6009/20, paragraph 23. Available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-6009-2020-INIT/en/pdf>

⁵⁰ Case C-166/07, *Parliament v. Council, International Fund for Ireland* ("IFI"), EU:C:2009:499.

*adaptability in the aims pursued by the Community legislature when it wishes to provide for common actions. Consequently, the priority areas of action change regularly in accordance with the economic and social needs which manifest themselves in various Member States.”*⁵¹ He considers “*the policy of cohesion may be defined as a device for restoring a balance and for redistribution among the Member States*”, while it is “*also an expression of solidarity between them and their peoples.*”⁵²

With that guidance from the Court, Article 175(3) TFEU has particularly started to acquire the quality of a general welfare clause in the recent past. The use of this legal basis is a relative novelty that dates back only to 2002.⁵³ But, of all past uses of this legal basis, the RRF, like its antecedents the Reform Support Programme and the BICC, make extensive use of this legal basis in an unprecedented way represent “*a move away from the domain of cohesion in the strict sense*”.⁵⁴

As noted above as regards US federalism, the Supreme Court has interpreted the General Welfare Clause: firstly, as precluding the promotion of the “particular welfare” of a specific state; and, secondly, as a “Spending Power” and not as a power to regulate to promote the “general welfare”.⁵⁵ Let us turn to that, more significant, second bar on regulation in the context of Article 175 TFEU. In that regard, the publically available Council Legal Service Opinion on the proposed Mechanism to resolve legal and administrative obstacles in a cross-border context⁵⁶ sheds light on the relationship between Article 175 and other regulatory legal bases. The Council Legal Service spells out that Article 3(3) TEU and Articles 174 TFEU and 175 TFEU set up “*a one way relationship between cohesion and other Union policies*”. The CLS frame this “one way” interaction as the Treaties stipulating that the formulation and implementation of Union policies, in particular the implementation of the internal market, contribute to the achievement of the overarching objective of economic, social and territorial cohesion, but, by contrast, *cohesion "actions" cannot be taken with*

⁵¹ Point 81 of the AG’s Opinion, EU:C:2009:213.

⁵² Point 85 of the AG’s Opinion, *supra*.

⁵³ It is noted that other instruments that have been adopted on the basis of the third subparagraph of Article 175 TFEU include the European Union Solidarity Fund (Regulation (EC) No 2012/2002 establishing the European Union Solidarity Fund), the European Globalisation Adjustment Fund (Regulation (EU) No 1309/2013 on the European Globalisation Adjustment Fund), the Structural Reform Support Programme (Regulation (EU) 2017/825 on the establishment of the Structural Reform Support Programme for the period 2017 to 2020), the European Fund for Strategic Investment (Regulation (EU) 2015/1017 on the European Fund for Strategic Investment, the European Investment Advisory Hub and the European Investment Project Portal, the “EFSI”) and Regulation (EC) 1968/2006 concerning Community financial contributions to the International Fund for Ireland (and successor regulations).

⁵⁴ B. De Witte (n 14).

⁵⁵ D. Engdahl (n 34); *cf.* S. Schwartz (n 33).

⁵⁶ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on a mechanism to resolve legal and administrative obstacles in a cross-border context, COM/2018/373 final.

*the preponderant aim of achieving the Union objectives in other policy areas.*⁵⁷ That latter regard the Council Legal Service identify a fundamental disanalogy between the case law on Article 114 TFEU, as such *Tobacco Advertising I* mentioned above, and Article 175 TFEU.

As such, the CLS go on to note that Mechanism applies to those situations where the "legal provisions of [a Member State] would constitute a legal obstacle hampering the implementation of a joint Project (...)" (Article 1(1) of the proposal, emphasis added). The Mechanism defines the notions of "legal provision" and "legal obstacle" in "*wide and unqualified terms*", simply by reference to the cross-border projects in respect of which they would apply or arise. Legal obstacles refer to any legal provision - including both legislative and administrative provisions, as well as administrative practices - that relates to the planning, development, staffing, financing or functioning of a joint project and that obstructs the inherent potential of border regions when interacting across the border. The upshot of fact that the Mechanism can apply to "*any field or subject in an unqualified manner potentially*" is that it "*opens its scope to remits other than cohesion for which the Treaties may establish specific EU competences and procedures, or for which the Union would hold no competence at all.*"⁵⁸

The "one way" relationship is specified itself in the express words of Article 175(3) TFEU itself, the "specific actions" that the EU legislator may adopt outside the Funds to achieve the objectives of cohesion under the third paragraph of Article 175 TFEU must not prejudice "the measures decided upon within the framework of the other Union policies" nor can those actions be used with the preponderant aim of achieving the Union objectives in other policy areas or extend beyond the scope of the Union cohesion policy.

Examples of where cohesion actions under Article 175 TFEU could adversely affect other Union policies are also set out by the CLS especially since the Mechanism was identified as capable of applying to of obstacles arising from the civil procedural law of two Member States, for which the Treaties establish a legal basis in Article 81 TFEU on judicial cooperation in civil matters. Equally, due to the extensive framing of the cohesion policy, it could apply in respect of legal obstacles arising from the application of different tax regimes, for which the Treaties lay down harmonisation powers, especially see Articles 113 and 115 TFEU, or it could apply in relation to social policy for which the Article 151 TFEU establishes specific rules and procedures, including the adoption of

⁵⁷ Opinion of the Council Legal Service (n 49), paragraph 28.

⁵⁸*Ibid*, paragraph 47.

measures designed to encourage cooperation between Member States (see Article 153(2)(a) and Article 156 TFEU).⁵⁹

In CLS Mechanism Opinion is of particular relevance as regards the RRF, insofar as its scope is “curiously” broad, and includes a wide range of objectives outside cohesion, as De Witte has noted most forcefully:

“The fact that the RRF Regulation is, in turn, based on Article 175(3) is again justified by stating its objective “to promote the Union’s economic, social and territorial cohesion”⁹⁵ but, within the same sentence, a dozen more objectives are added that correspond to the different policy strands of the RRF. Even more curiously, Article 3 of the Regulation (entitled “Scope”) mentions “economic cohesion” and “social and territorial cohesion” as two of the six pillars of the Facility, thereby giving the impression that the other four pillars (namely, green transition, digital transformation, crisis preparedness, and policies for the next generation) are not about cohesion. This could seem to question the suitability of Article 175(3) as the legal basis, but one should maybe not read too much into the text of Article 3. One could very well consider that, whereas two constitutive elements of cohesion are explicitly highlighted as pillars of the programme, cohesion in general is still the overarching ambition of the RRF programme as a whole. Anyway, one can see a clear confirmation of a trend foreshadowed in the previous instruments based on Article 175(3), namely a move away from the domain of cohesion in the strict sense (namely, the sort of measures funded by the structural funds) towards a much broader domain of macro-economic policy measures aiming at improving the overall balance of economic development within the territory of the European Union.”⁶⁰

There are two questions raised by this. This first is with respect to the substantive scope of RRFs. In particular, a number of milestones and targets include “education and skills” and “health”, where it is the competence of the Union to carry out actions to support, coordinate or supplement the actions of the Member States, excludes the approximation of laws and is expressly circumscribed by reserve competences. Suffice it to note in this connection that Article 168(7) TFEU states: “Union action shall respect the responsibilities of the Member States for the definition of their health policy and for the organisation and delivery of health services and medical care. The responsibilities of the Member States shall include the management of health services and medical care and the allocation of the resources assigned to them. The measures referred to in paragraph 4(a) shall not affect

⁵⁹ *Ibid*, paragraph 48.

⁶⁰ B. De Witte (n 14), p. 658.

national provisions on the donation or medical use of organs and blood.” Likewise, Article 165(1) TFEU reads: “The Union shall contribute to the development of quality education by encouraging cooperation between Member States and, if necessary, by supporting and supplementing their action, while fully respecting the responsibility of the Member States for the content of teaching and the organisation of education systems and their cultural and linguistic diversity.”

The second question raised is with respect to economic policy coordination. Flynn sets out the position that cohesion programmes may have “indirect effects” on that policy field in these terms:

“the fact that the effects of the measure will have an impact on economic policy does not mean that the use of that other legal base constitutes a circumvention of the limitations associated with Article 121 TFEU. The Court accepted in Gauweiler and Weiss that monetary policy measures taken by the European Central Bank (‘ECB’) do not fall into the sphere of economic policy for the sole reason that they may have indirect effects that can also be sought in the context of economic policy. By the same logic, measures adopted by the other Union institutions under other policies are not equivalent to economic policy measures due to such indirect effects. Moreover, the fact that such effects are definitely foreseeable by the measure’s author(s) and are knowingly accepted does not rob them of the status of ‘indirect’ effects”⁶¹

The “one way” relationship of the kind set out by the CLS seems to call into question the appropriateness of a cohesion policy instrument like the RRFs to be integrated and indeed replace instruments of the European Semester, as the Commission specified, *per* the 2021 Annual Growth Survey, in relation to the country-specific recommendations of 2021.

In that context, the CLS’s Mechanism opinion offers a theory of where the scope of Article 175 TFEU ends that while not limiting its role to a Spending Power (“specific actions” in the wording clearly extend beyond this) would prevent Article 175 TFEU from transforming into a regulatory legal basis. The tests spelled out in *Dole*, in the context of the RRF, provide little clarity, apart from the fourth criterion on coercion. As set out in *Sebelius*, the extent of federal funding can indicate coercion. The size of the RRF support in that context would be somewhat indicative of coercion⁶², especially given that, while Member States enjoy autonomous tax bases in a way US states do not, in a crisis they have little fiscal space that would enable them to forego RRF support.

⁶¹ L. Flynn (n 18), p. 48.

⁶² <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/infographics/RRF/?lang=en#data-map>

4. Conclusion: A fiscal capacity that incentivises without dragooning

NGEU presents many legal novelties that are a testament to the ingenuity and adaptability of reflections on a fiscal capacity for the EMU and its governance that were already in progress when the COVID-19 pandemic erupted. This paper has examined what NGEU, and in particular the RRF, “does” to the structure of federalism in the EU. The RRF makes a sweeping use of cohesion policy to deliver funds in return for the satisfaction of milestones and targets setting out detailed reforms and investments. After arguing that we can viably discuss the EU as a federation, the paper proceeded to examine like conditional spending programmes that are hallmarks of coercive federalism in the US, Australia and Canada. In that context, the enumeration or conferral principle is re-contextualised and conditional spending has, across the jurisdictions examined, been recognised as legitimately pursuing *extraneous ends of the general welfare*. The US jurisprudence nonetheless provides a heuristic framework for thinking about whether conditional spending may cross the line between policy leverage and policy dragooning. Turning to the RRF, and its legal basis Article 175(3) TFEU, we found that it has features in common with a general welfare clause and carries the risk of exercising regulatory power in fields that are subject to other Union policies or no Union competence at all. In that sense, the risk to the federal structure is the same as that carried by conditional spending programmes in the US.

Except as to the size of the support, the *Dole* tests do not really seem to suggest that the RRF has a coercive character that would satisfy the legal definition of compulsion at least. In the final analysis, it would be a mistake to reify the doctrines set out in *Sebelius* and *Dole*, as well as the bar on regulation under the general welfare clause. The real value of these doctrines lies in their capacity to speak to a deeper set of problems and the “politico-legal” basis of the pact making up the federation. The inquiry should not be limited to asking only where the federal programme at issue rises to the level of “mere coercion” but help us to understand if the fiscal capacity that the EU is husbanding leaves sufficient policy space for Member States and their legislatures to exercise real choice over whether to accept funding and to fashion the conditions that are tied to it. The larger a fiscal capacity is, the more specific the Union parameters on the design of RRFs and the more it purports to regulate matters that are subject to other Union policies or a reserve power, the less effective choice is afforded to the Member State. The danger of coercive federalism is one we should be alive to in designing “de-crisisified” successors to NGEU.